

Impact of AI on Leadership Strategies

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Ms.Sneha Singh
Brindavan College

Dr.Meenakshi Verma
REVA University

Abstract

With the advent of AI in almost all spheres of the corporate world, there has been a strong influence on all the fundamentals of Organization Behaviour and Human Resources Management. AI is now acting as a triggering force for the refinement of Leaders and their Leadership strategies across all levels. There now exists a demand for paradigm shift in leadership styles across the cross sections of the organization. After realizing the importance of this shift and most importantly adopting this new and pertinent change in the system, organizations are left with little or no choice but to vehemently follow this new ghost named AI.

There have been numerous studies that have been conducted globally assessing the change in leadership styles amongst HR after the dawn of AI. This study focusses on the negative and positive impact that AI has brought about amongst the employees of middle level management in the IT sector. My study also lays emphasis on future business strategies pertaining leadership that the employees will have to adhere to. With a strong belief that impact of AI on leadership whether positive or negative is yet to be debated, yet it has left all the corporate world with many learning opportunities.

Keywords: AI, OB, HRM, Leadership, Middle Management, IT sector.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence is another branch of computer science which emphasizes on creating the intellectual machines that work and react like humans. Some of the activities artificial intelligence is designed to perform include Speech Recognition, Learning, Planning and problem solving. Artificial intelligence has become an essential part of the technology by making a global presence and strong impact with the creation of conversational chatbots, self-driving cars, and recommendation systems. Also AI has not only spreaded its wing in Healthcare, Finance, Education or Transportation Industry but the remarkable changes can also be seen in the manner today Human Resource activities are performed. AI is spreading its reputation among business leaders as an emerging asset to the workforce and also transforming the way businesses and societies operate.

In an era where Innovation, Cost Reduction, Improved productivity, Workforce Management has been a continuous

challenge, one particular technology stands out among business leaders which has high potential impact to overcome the challenges with greater efficiency and that is Artificial intelligence (AI). According to the 2018 Future Enterprise survey from Seyfarth Shaw LLP, 62% of the business leaders said that automation and AI would have the biggest impact on their business's operations and processes over the next five years. According to research firm Gartner, AI will eliminate 1.8 million jobs by 2020, but will create 2.3 million more in the same time frame. Others have argued that AI may destroy more jobs than it creates, while 69% of executives in a 2017 Deloitte report said that AI won't kill jobs.

But at the same time we all must understand that AI is going to revolutionise the way next generation business world and leaders are going to work. This thought led a very few thought proving questions - How does AI affect leadership? Is artificial intelligence as a threat to human leadership? At this juncture, its needed to understand that the very purpose of AI is to Augment, Learning, Planning, Improve quality, leading towards ultimately replacing Human Intelligence. And in this regard, there is no reason to believe that AI will not have strong influence on new era of leadership. This study is going to be completely a conceptual study which will explore the impact of AI on leadership with its advantages and disadvantages. To proceed, various Articles and few research papers published on various journals and on international universities websites have been reviewed.

Objectives

1. To study the Impact of AI in leadership strategies.
2. To analyse the positive and Negative impact of AI in Middle Level Management

Need for the Study

Great business leaders are known for their ability and potential to see and visualize what others do not. They take challenges, motivate and inspire their teams to think bigger, better, bolder and perform effectively. Here, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is finally yielding valuable and smart inputs and changing the competitive landscape in several industry followed by the change in leadership style. Hence its been found that there is a need for the in-depth study on how the leadership style is being change and to what extent. This study will address the AI impact on leadership.

Review of Literature

McKinsey Quarterly (2018) shows how the artificial intelligence makes the leadership in the present world. The relationship between ideas and technology in the modern world resulted in the machine learning process which makes the world of better clarity, specificity, and creativity. The study shows how the artificial intelligence reduces the burden of the business organisations to make them more productive in the fields of HR and finance, supply and communication etc. It is believed that robots replace the human resource in the future world however the Artificial Intelligence that powers the future robotic world shall be mastered by the human resource. Such human resource shall have high intelligence and analytical skills. Thus the AI has major role in shaping the future leadership.

According to Laura Cox (2018) focuses on the leadership qualities in the era of Artificial intelligence. The leaders of Artificial intelligence era need to understand the potentials of the people and design the products according to their needs. Understanding the hard and soft technologies will be the mandatory requirement for the leadership in the era of Artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence will also reduce the traditional hierarchy in the business organisations. This will also narrow down the decisions of the business organisations.

A study conducted by Rohit Talwar, Steve Wells and Alexandra (2017) identifies the leadership challenges in implementing the Artificial Intelligence in workplace. The article also discusses various developmental issues of AI in the future world. Rapid development in AI may decrease the complex roles in the business organisations so that the human resource shall develop the extra-unique qualities to compete with the technological race. Human resource department has greater role in deciding the performance of the working population of the organisation. The article suggests implementing soft skill training programmes to balance between artificial intelligence and the workforce.

According to SasheKanapathi, he recognizes that how job roles can replace humans with robotics. The Article also discusses the various changes happening in world due to the Artificial Intelligence. AI is focused on being prepared for the future change. The entire world turning as a digital world and it emphasis on business and life, competencies plays a major role in leader's career to survive in the new digital world of Industry.

Impact of AI on Leadership Strategies

Leaders to be more Agile

Firstly AI can be a huge aid to the leader whose aim to become more inwardly agile and foster creative approaches to transformation. AI with its fast data processing and high computational ability creates its own empirical feedback loop which will allows the leaders to think and behave as an experimental science lab leading to the tremendous transformation in leadership quality, style and performance improvement. AI as a significant enabler will save a lot of time of new era of leaders by fast processing and consolidation of information. So leaders will have more time to think and work on people Management, creativity and innovation making them more agile.

A Shift in Style

Secondly, Traditional leadership qualities emphasized on strength, decisiveness, ability to motivate, persuade and successfully carry out a plan. Though these personality traits are still valued in leaders today but in the face of Artificial Intelligence, business leadership is undergoing a further shift. The result of which are AI bringing up the fundamental and remarkable changes in new era of leadership qualities and style. It is obviously very likely to happen that AI will supplant many aspects of the “hard” skills of leadership — that is, cognitive processing of facts and information, Fast learning, Planning, Data Computing but at the same time, how AI will supplant the “soft” elements or skills of leadership such as emotional intelligence, the various personality traits, attitudes, and behaviours which makes an individual a LEADER and help others to achieve a common goal or shared purpose, is a matter to think and analyse. We can say that Leaders are definitely going to be leveraged by Artificial Intelligence. But at the same time leaders of the AI age must be in a position to gage the potential of their workforce with greater understanding, empower them, and helps taking out their best performance with high efficiency. And for this the soft element of leadership style or personality traits need to be imbibed in new age leaders and in the manner they work. A famous writer and Philosopher Lancefield explains that the most effective leaders do both and can do both.

Eliminating the Business Hierarchy

As AI gradually taking over the responsibilities traditionally carried out by the leaders, will this effect business hierarchy? Here the famous Author and philosopher Lancefield says that though some of the activities of leaders will be actually carried out by AI but still there will always be a need of figureheads. The task and responsibilities of taking quick decision, task delegation,

motivational talk and discussion to boost their morale, emotional intelligence and many more such needed traits will support the very much existence of figureheads. so AI not going to completely eliminate the business hierarchy but yes digital leaders will have a way through AI to simplify the organisation and cut through the hierarchy to the extent. Too many organisations have too many layers, and too much bureaucracy which can be helped by AI.

Positive Impact of AI on Middle Management Employees

As we all know that Artificial intelligence is transforming the way business world operating. Machines are now performing a wide range of physical and cognitive tasks. And the efficiency, effectiveness and accuracy of business process work is expected to increase as AI systems are advancing through machine learning, big data and increased computational power, impacting greatly on job prospect and talent search at middle level employment.. There has been a common understanding that the advent of new technology might strip many people of their livelihoods. But actually this kind of automation improves not only organisation but society as a whole and raises standard of living. Here are a few following ways on how AI is making a positive impact.

Find the Best Human Resource

Organization using AI for personnel management, are rapidly adopting advance Technologies and AI to help them find the best candidates for their jobs. Such software often works in one of two ways: spotting the most promising resumes, or widening the net so larger that employers finds more diverse pool of prospective candidates .They are using specific matrices and comparative analysis to cull out candidates who seem to be the most suitable for the job scratching through the endless list to cherry picking the best, AI helps organizations in finding and comparing the rate of efficiencies and potential of different candidates, even before they get hired

Hunting on Employees Emotion Quotient

Artificial intelligence is aiding managers to understand employee's personal aspects of job performance which can help them analyse their level of efficiency. AI analyses employees email, social media and other messages, looking and analysing words, sentences and phrases employees use, leading to the expression for positive or negative sentiment. This helps in supervising individual as well as group morale, Behaviour, values and ethical standards. It also detects any changes in tone or a shift in relationship within the employees or group , eliminating the chances of a potential conflict.

Tracking Down Employees Activities

Artificial intelligence can help managers measure the efficiency and productivity of employees by tracking how they handle various aspects of their jobs including their computer activities. The system or software can be encrypted in a manner where it logs everything done on their desktop taking periodic screenshots, saving it for a month ensuring privacy. Then, an artificial intelligence can determine a touch base for company's activities and searches for incongruities contributing to poor productivity. Customers can set activities and thresholds that can trigger an alert and if the software detects anything suspicious, it will send notification to management. This helps out the problematic areas of employees and helping them overcoming it.

Retention of Top Performers on Board

A surprising yet truly possible concept, AI can help predict when employees are planning wind up their career in that particular company - and provides measures and solutions on how to retain

them. The AI system identifies the pattern by own matrices to predict when employees are likely to shift from the job. It considers various factors affecting job satisfaction and calculates a risk score for individual employees. The software also feeds suggestions as a immediate on immediate steps to be taken, helping managers in retaining valuable work force. The retention - risk score is one of the best aid by AI as it helps leaders preventing the loss of potential manpower further leading to increased loyalty and productivity.

Negative Impact of AI on Middle Management Employees

Artificial intelligence and machine learning are controlling the business world at a rapid pace, and there has been a lot of attention to its impact on employment on Middle level Management. Though lot of positive impact has been discussed but we just cannot denied with its negative impact. Its needed to understand that what happens if Machine learning/ AI end up taking jobs from humans and how this will affect the employees and organisation as a whole. Emerging technologies improves the speed, quality, and cost of business and services, but at the same time, it might displace large numbers of human resource at middle level. This possibility challenges the traditional mode of working and benefits of jobs.

Few of the experts disagree and few argue on the size of the impact that automation technologies will have on the employees. Others point out that technology may create new job categories that will employ displaced workers but its still a matter of debate without any surety.

Conclusion

AI – will embrace the future leaders with more advanced and enhanced leadership skills. As discussed above, future leaders will have a lot of AI intervention in analysing data for decision-making, and hence they will get more time in taking care of their people and other creative aspect. Leaders will also have AI’s help in monitoring the performance of their people, but at the same time, they must put more effort to uphold the values of the organisation. As of now, we are not seeing AI penetrating much on the softs skills of leadership but as the technologies are advancing, its predicted that the day will come soon. To conclude, the core need for leadership remains as of now AI and machine learning can help create better leaders.

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